

METHODS OF DETERMINING SEISMIC WEAKNESS E GRI LINES FOR STONE BRICK BUILDINGS IN NAMANGAN CITY

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ABSTRACT

This research work is essential for large-scale seismic risk assessment of residential buildings to predict post-earthquake losses and to implement emergency response, risk reduction and preparedness strategies, and to prioritize reconstruction measures to be implemented in the building stock. Accurate estimation of the socio-economic damage caused by future earthquakes is also important for the insurance and reinsurance industries and for the allocation of financial resources. In the course of the study, taking into account the multifaceted practical implications, the methods of assessing seismic risk and seismic effects in several stages are considered.

Keywords: *Seismic Vulnerability Curves, Seismic Vulnerability, Seismic Hazard, Post-Earthquake Damage Information, MSK-64, Seismicity, Monitoring, Vs30, Geological, Non-Seismic Brick Buildings.*

INTRODUCTION.

Undoubtedly, the damage and losses that may occur due to future earthquakes can be effectively reduced only by the proper use of research methods available in reliable and accurate risk assessment. In this context, the main difficulty is that seismic risk assessment requires the analysis of various data, which is the result of combining seismic risk, impact and seismic vulnerability. Other components (ie, damage loss functions) can then be introduced to relate the damage to consequences such as social or economic loss. Seismic vulnerability, which represents the susceptibility of buildings to earthquake damage, is a risk component that mainly includes engineering data and can be evaluated by different approaches, usually divided into empirical, analytical, expert-judgmental and hybrid methods.

Not another method, when it is necessary to choose one, it depends on the nature of the data and the purpose of the research. Damage data from observations can be affected by several issues that require careful consideration and precise handling to obtain a reliable quantification of seismic vulnerability. Nevertheless, due to statistical data, empirical approaches are effective tools in seismic vulnerability characterization, particularly in regional applications.

This paper presents an empirical model of seismicity used to assess the seismic vulnerability of regional brick residential buildings. The seismic damage model was

developed with the need to follow the basic features of construction engineering. Vulnerability functions were built on the basis of the damage assessment of structures under seismic effects determined using the program "GESI_programm" for the assessment of the seismic resistance of brick residential buildings [2],.

This program was developed in 1999-2001 as part of the pilot project of the United Nations "Global Earthquake Safety Initiative (GESI) Pilot Project". The primary material, that is, the results of the data collected within the framework of the international RADIUS project served as a basis for the development of the program. In 1998-1999, a conference was held by the UN-IDNDR secretariat (Risk Assessment Tools for Diagnosis of Urban Areas against Seismic Disasters), in which Addis Ababa (Ethiopia), Antofagasta (Chile), Bandung (Indonesia), Guayaquil (Ecuador), Zigong (China), Izmir (Turkey), Skopje (Macedonia), Tashkent (Uzbekistan) and Tijuana (Mexico) cities based on scientific and practical results.

Vulnerability functions were built using the computer program "GESI_Program" to assess the vulnerability of selected types of buildings, which are based on the assessment of structural damage under certain seismic effects [1,2].

Although components cannot be edited in seismic hazard assessment, it is possible to use software-defined PGA values for seismic vulnerability classes of buildings. Therefore, the characterization of seismic vulnerability according to the fragility curve and the classification of seismic vulnerability of brick residential buildings constitute the main part of the established methodology. The general approach on which the proposed model relies in terms of key assumptions to determine the data source and reliable damage database is seen in the paper. In order to evaluate the fragility curve and model the seismic vulnerability composition of the building stock, the main components are considered separately, respectively[4,5,6].

Discussion of the results:

This paper proposes a fragility model derived empirically by statistical processing of damage data collected after historical seismic events in Namangan city. Information about the damage In 1494, the Namangan earthquake of magnitude 5 M, located at a depth of 6 km, was observed. This earthquake caused damage of 8-9 points on the MSK-64 scale[3]. In 1927, another Namangan earthquake of magnitude 6 M, located at a depth of 14 km, occurred in the same cracks . We can see that -64 is equal to 8 points on the scale . The research was based on the damage observed in these earthquakes, including incomplete post-earthquake field surveys as one of the possible sources of uncertainty affecting observational damage data. This problem usually occurs in locations far from the source of the earthquake, where post-earthquake surveys may not have been accurately evaluated by the owner of the residential building alone. As a result, the damage distribution is inaccurate due to an underestimation of the number of undamaged buildings, as often the owners of damaged buildings do not allow inspection of the building. In order to solve this problem, literature studies have chosen sources where the uninspected buildings were assumed to be undamaged (for example, Namangan in 1494-1927)

or only those sources where the percentage of inspected buildings exceeded a pre-selected limit, indicated as the limit of completeness. In this work, the completeness ratio (i.e., the number of inspected buildings over the total number of buildings from the census) was selected and edited to create a damage dataset above 90%.

Unexamined buildings in less affected areas were combined by characterizing them with lower PGA levels, considering that they were most likely undamaged, and were evaluated based on the selected scenario earthquakes[7,8].

This selected earthquake scenario is based on the Namangan earthquake of 1927 with a magnitude of 6 M and a depth of 14 km. As a result of the earthquake, we can see that the area of Namangan city was equal to 8 points on the MSK-64 scale.

"INTensity MAP v3.0" software was used to select the earthquake scenario. The "INTensity MAP v3.02" program was developed by specialists of the Institute of Seismology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of seismic risk assessment (No. DGU 09237) and is presented in Fig1.

INTensity MAP v 4.0

$$I = 1.475 * M - 2.646 * \lg H + 1.905 - 0.498 * M * \lg(R/H) + 1.159 * \lg H * \lg(R/H) - 1.401 * \lg(R/H)$$

M-magnitude
H-gulibina
R-hypocentral distance (distance to source at depth)

percent.1	percent.2	percent.3
1,475	2,646	1,905
percent.4	percent.5	percent.6
0,498	1,159	1,401

Latitude: 41,009
Longitude: 71,646

M-magnitude: 6
H-distance at depth: 14

Energy earthquake: 7

defined delete

Fig 1. Interface of "INTensity MAP v4.0" software

Fig. 2 Isoseismic map with the parameters of the earthquake scenario according to the "INTensity MAP v4.0" program for the 1927 Namangan earthquake ($x=71,646$, $y=41,009$, $M=6$, $h=14$ km).

Fig 3. Seismic vulnerability values in neighborhood cross-sections for brick buildings are given in points for the selected series of earthquakes

Using the statistical measurement and typological construction data collected in the post-earthquake survey forms, the statistical data of the building dataset was carried out according to the databases of different buildings, such as the number of floors and construction age, and the type of vertical and horizontal structures. Figure 4 shows the data on the construction age of the buildings[9,10].

Fig 4. Distribution of residential buildings built in the city of Namangan by years of construction

In the city of Namangan, most of the brick buildings were built before 1900 (36%), and a significant part of the structures were built before 1919 (57%). According to the information provided in the survey forms, brick buildings are classified according to the type of vertical and horizontal structures. Different forms of research were used to assess the damage and serviceability of residential buildings after two seismic events, including a further process of data interpretation aimed at classifying the data according to the same damage and building classification systems[10].

Seismic vulnerability is characterized by indicators of damages and erosions that can occur as a result of an earthquake in the structures of buildings and structures. The calculation of the seismic vulnerability curve required the description of the seismic effect in damaged areas of buildings and structures, the determination of discrete levels of damage and the adoption of a typological classification system. After processing the raw data, the observed damage data were identified in a statistical model, which analyzes the earthquake level of seismic vulnerability. and the seismic risk was estimated based on peak acceleration values within the platform. PGA values are selected, these data are obtained on the basis of seismic scales developed by scientists of the Institute of Seismology of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The maps according to peak acceleration

values used in this study were based on research results based on the estimation of local areas based on average S-wave velocity in the top 30m (V_{s30}). In the case of the Namangan earthquake, in this case, it is possible to provide a continuous description, taking into account the availability of accurate geo-verified damage data. The seismic vulnerability curve for brick buildings below was determined by inputting data into the "GESI_programm" program[11].

Fig 5. Vulnerability function for the masonry building.

Correspondence of building typologies to vulnerability classes and definition of fragility curves requires the determination of fragility curves for seismic vulnerability classes by using national seismic risk data for regional hazard programs.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a method for calculating empirical seismic vulnerability curves for residential (fired brick) buildings, evaluated on post-earthquake damage data in Namangan city and corresponding to the main features of the national seismic hazard platform. Seismic vulnerability. It is characterized by seismic vulnerability functions and then processed based on building height. To this end, a clustering strategy is implemented to combine predefined building typologies into vulnerability classes based on the similarity of observed seismic vulnerability. On the other hand, a special computer program was developed to determine the seismic vulnerability composition of the open building stock, starting from the cadastral data registration data. The empirically obtained seismic vulnerability function for brick buildings was

included in the seismic vulnerability function group established for other residential buildings and together with other vulnerability functions was used to assess the seismic risk of Namangan city. The results presented in this paper can also be used to estimate the seismic risk and the expected seismic risk in similar facilities of the building inventory.

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